

A STUDY ON THE LEVEL OF STRESS ASSOCIATED WITH IT EMPLOYEES IN COIMBATORE

Surabhi Krishnan* & Dr. K. Niranjanaa Devi**

* Research Scholar, Dr. G. R. Damodaran Academy of Management,
Coimbatore, Tamilnadu

** Professor in management, Dr. G. R. Damodaran Academy of Management,
Neelambur, Coimbatore, Tamilnadu

Cite This Article: Surabhi Krishnan & Dr. K. Niranjanaa Devi, “A Study on the Level of Stress Associated With It Employees in Coimbatore”, International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Modern Education, Volume 4, Issue 2, Page Number 6-11, 2018.

Copy Right: © IJMRME, 2018 (All Rights Reserved). This is an Open Access Article distributed under the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium provided the original work is properly cited.

Abstract:

Stress is basically the Impact of one object on another. There are three terms which are used synonymously to denote this phenomenon stress, strain, and pressure, however, there are thin differences in these terms. Stress is a term basically used in physical sciences which means pressure of one object on another. The main objective of the study is to find out the stress details regarding the IT employees in Coimbatore region and to study the impact and usefulness of Work Stress Management and also to suggest measures for coping with stress. For this purpose a sample of 200 was collected from the respondents were percentage analysis, chi-square, descriptive statistics, factor analysis and correlation were used as tools to analyse the data. The conclusion is that the companies with IT industry can carry out a workplace audit to assess stress levels and they can develop policies and procedures that support employee well being and the employees also feel that language is one of the barrier in work place and for this the management can coordinate the employees based on their language so that a friendly atmosphere will be created in working place which leads to increase in productivity of the firms with IT industry.

Key Words: Stress, Policies & Work Place

Introduction to the Study:

Organizational life is quite stressful new technologies, global competition, Competitive pressures, have multiplied the woes of employees in recent times. Workers who are stressed are also more likely to be unhealthy, poorly motivated, less productive and less safe at work. Their organizations are less likely to be successful in a competitive market.

Stress is the “wear and tear” of our bodies experience as we adjust to our continually changing environment; it has physical and emotional effects on us and can create positive or negative feelings. As positive influences, stress can help compel us to action; it can result in a new awareness and an exciting new perspective. As a negative influence it can result in feelings of destruct, rejection, anger and depression, which in turn can lead to health problem such as headache, upset stomach, rashes, insomnia, ulcers, high blood pressure, heart diseases and stroke.

Causes of Stress:

There may be numerous conditions in which people may feel stress. Conditions that tend to cause stress are called stressors. Although even a single stressor may cause major stress, like death of near one, usually stressors combine to press an individual in a variety of ways until stress develops. The various stressors can be grouped into four categories: individual, group, organizational and extra organizational. Within each category, there may be several stressors.

Statement of Problem:

To find the perception and satisfaction of the employees about various welfare and social facilities offered by the company to its employees and their stress level in the company. Immigrant workers at IT companies in Coimbatore area live as a community and facing several problems such as low wages, health hazards, exploitation, denial of the rights, satisfy in work place, hostel facilities, food facilities and recreation

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To find out the Stress details regarding the It employees in Coimbatore region.
- ✓ To analyze the impact of stress work in the society.
- ✓ To gain a better understanding of the migrant worker population in Coimbatore area, with regard to numbers, employment trends and a range of demographic characteristics.
- ✓ To make relevant recommendations arising out of the research.

Scope of the Study:

This study will enable us to find out how much the recreation system will help the employee and improve the overall performance of the IT companies. And can measure the attitude of employees and management towards the effectiveness role of the stress.

This study aimed to collect demographic information about the new communities, gain understanding about the spoken languages, age groups, education etc.

- ✓ This study will identify employment conditions.
- ✓ This study will enable to identify housing and living conditions.
- ✓ This study will help to identify skills and qualifications held by the migrant workers.
- ✓ This study aimed to find out the food facility, hostel facility, leave facility and the recreations provided by the firm for migrant workers.

Research Methodology:

Research Design:

A research is the arrangement of condition for the collection and analysis of data in a manner that aims to combine relevance to search purpose with the economy in procedure.

Relevance of the Study:

Human Resource Development uses various techniques, performance analysis, training and development, career planning and development, etc. for employees growth and organizations growth as well. Role of Stress level deals with various aspects of work environment, which facilitates the human resource development efficiently.

Tools of Data Collection:

The main tools of data collection were observation, questionnaire, and interview method. The interview and questionnaire methods consisted of almost all aspects economic, social, and cultural.

The interview method was selected as the tool for the data collection because the researcher felt that if respondents are personally interviewed, the investigator can create fair atmosphere by explaining the purpose of the study, and can assure the confidential nature of the data and doubts about the questions can also be cleared.

Population and Samples:

The population of the study constitutes the people working in IT companies in Coimbatore. The sample size taken for the study was 200.

Types of Data Collected:

For this study, primary and secondary data was used. Primary data was collected through the methods like questionnaire, interview, observation and schedule.

Secondary data was collected through the literature such as newspapers, books, articles, journals, magazines, text books.

Sample Size:

Statistical Tools Used: Simple percentage analysis, Chi – Square test, factor analysis, descriptive statistics and Correlation.

Limitations of the Study:

- ✓ There may be a bias in primary data collection of the study.
- ✓ Since there were certain limitations to meet the respondents directly inside the organization the data was collected through a third party, and hence the data may not be relevant.
- ✓ Main drawback is language barrier.
- ✓ Time limit.

Analysis and Interpretation:

Percentage Analysis:

		Frequency	Percentage
Age	20 to 25	140	70
	26 to 30	60	30
	Total	200	100
Educational Qualification	10 th class	148	74
	Pre-Degree	28	14
	Under Graduation	24	12
	Total	200	100
Marital status	Married	96	48
	Unmarried	104	52
	Total	200	100
Type of family	Nuclear	124	62
	Joint	76	38
	Total	200	100

Chi Square:

Demographic Profiles (Age) and Level of Acceptance of Employees:

H0: There is no significant relationship between age and level of acceptance of employees towards stress.

Level of Acceptance of Employees	Chi-Square Value	P Value	Result
Opinion of the respondents on each day work appears as though it will never end	7.548	0.110	Accept
Respondents depressions away from their family	5.605	0.231	Accept
Opinion of the respondents about friendliness with the locality people	11.348	0.023	Reject
Opinion of the respondents satisfy their work	10.871	0.028	Reject
Respondents towards the working condition	3.610	0.461	Accept
Opinion of the respondents felt that language is a barrier at the place of work	0.566	0.967	Accept
Respondent's opinion about feel comfortable to work with the local people.	6.572	0.160	Accept
Opinion of the respondents the job really demanding	2.983	0.561	Accept
Opinion of the respondents work involves deadlines that has to completed	1.290	0.863	Accept
Opinion of respondents entitled for casual leave	8.407	0.078	Accept
Opinion of the respondents satisfy with the leave facility	7.190	0.126	Accept
Respondents frequent chances to go to your hometown	4.087	0.394	Accept
Taking decisions on respondents satisfied with the food provided here.	4.613	0.329	Accept
Respondents opinion about the hostel facilities	5.393	0.249	Accept
Opinion of the respondents the mode of recreation that you sought to	6.381	0.172	Accept

Interpretation:

The above table shows about relationship between age and level of acceptance of employees towards stress. There is a relationship between age and Opinion of the respondents satisfy their work (0.028), Opinion of the respondents about friendliness with the locality people (0.023) as the level of significance is less than 0.05.

Correlation:

		Opinion towards the Job Interesting
Age	Pearson Correlation	0.027
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.701
	N	200
Educational qualification	Pearson Correlation	0.323
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0
	N	200
Marital status	Pearson Correlation	0.055
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.439
	N	200
Type of family	Pearson Correlation	0.149
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.035
	N	200

Interpretation:

The above table shows about correlation between demographic profiles age, educational qualification, marital status, type of family and opinion towards the job interesting. The correlation between Opinion towards the job interesting and age (0.027), Educational qualification (0.323), Marital status (0.055), and Type of family (0.149) were all the factors are positively correlated which shows that while taking decision on Opinion towards the job interesting all the demographic profiles used for the study can be taken for the decision making process of the study.

Factor Analysis:

A total of 15 variables were identified for the purpose of collecting acceptance of employees towards various factors. In order to reduce the number of variables and to identify the key factors contributing towards the level of acceptance, factor analysis is performed. KMO and Bartlett's test is conducted to identify the sampling adequacy.

KMO and Bartlett's Test for Level of Acceptance of Employees:

KMO and Bartlett's Test	
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.	0.55

Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	109.499
	df	105
	Sig.	0.362

KMO of sampling adequacy value for employee's level of acceptance measures is 0.550 and it indicates that the sample is adequate to consider the data as normally distributed.

The number of factors as identified by performing the screen plot. The results are shown below,

Rotated Component Matrix for Employee Level of Acceptance:

Rotated Component Matrix						
	Component					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
Opinion of the respondents on each day work appears as though it will never end	0.683	0.171	0.19	-0.068	0.051	-0.075
Respondents depressions away from their family	-0.245	0.045	-0.638	0.069	-0.154	-0.038
Opinion of the respondents about friendliness with the locality people	0.398	-0.07	0.126	-0.338	-0.275	-0.447
Opinion of the respondents satisfy their work	0.114	0.07	-0.092	-0.092	-0.064	0.79
Respondents towards the working condition	0.019	0.121	0.658	0.038	-0.024	-0.137
Opinion of the respondents felt that language is a barrier at the place of work	-0.12	-0.16	0.436	0.225	-0.203	0.392
Respondent's opinion about feel comfortable to work with the local people.	0.087	0.199	0.128	-0.331	0.274	0.296
Opinion of the respondents the job really demanding	-0.068	0.644	-0.043	-0.112	-0.133	0.044
Opinion of the respondents work involves deadlines that has to completed	0.424	0.009	-0.064	0.64	0.17	-0.077
Opinion of respondents entitled for casual leave	-0.366	-0.544	0.128	-0.098	0.033	0.122
Opinion of the respondents satisfy with the leave facility	0.056	0.017	-0.132	-0.084	0.702	0.092
Respondents frequent chances to go to your hometown	-0.039	-0.087	0.247	0.031	0.634	-0.178
Taking decisions on respondents satisfied with the food provided here.	-0.139	0.052	0.115	0.693	-0.14	0.042
Respondents opinion about the hostel facilities	-0.654	0.15	-0.025	-0.037	0	-0.18
Opinion of the respondents the mode of recreation that you sought to	-0.084	0.659	0.226	0.109	0.169	0.134
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis. Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.						
a. Rotation converged in 8 iterations.						

Interpretation:

From the above table, factors above the common values above 0.5 are considered and those factors are taken for decision making process of the study. The factors are Opinion of the respondents on each day work appears as though it will never end, respondents towards the working condition, opinion of the respondents the job really demanding, opinion of the respondents work involves deadlines that has to completed, respondents frequent chances to go to your hometown, taking decisions on respondents satisfied with the food provided here.

Descriptive Statistics:

	Mean	Std. Deviation
Opinion of the respondents on each day work appears as though it will never end	2.59	1.013
Respondents depressions away from their family	2.36	1.207
Opinion of the respondents about friendliness with the locality people	2.89	1.069

Interpretation:

The above table shows about descriptive statistics on level of acceptance of employees for various factors. The factors above average mean (2.24) are taken in to consideration for the decision making of the

study. The factors are opinion of the respondents on each day work appears as though it will never end, respondents depressions away from their family, opinion of the respondents about friendliness with the locality people, respondents opinion about feel comfortable to work with the local people., opinion of the respondents work involves deadlines that has to completed, and respondents frequent chances to go to your hometown.

Findings:

- ✓ Most of the respondents agree their work involves deadlines.
- ✓ Maximum of the respondents strongly agree that they entitled for casual leave.
- ✓ Most of the respondents are very much satisfied with the leave facility provided in the IT industry in Coimbatore.
- ✓ Majority of the respondents are rarely getting frequent chances to go to their hometown.
- ✓ Majority of the respondents strongly agree that they feel good hostel facilities.
- ✓ Maximum of respondent think that television is the best recreation mode in the It industry in Coimbatore.
- ✓ There is a significant relationship between age and opinion of the respondents satisfy their work, opinion of the respondents about friendliness with the locality people.
- ✓ There is a significant relationship between educational qualification and opinion of the respondents about friendliness with the locality people, opinion of the respondents satisfy their work, taking decisions on respondents satisfied with the food provided here and Opinion of the respondents the mode of recreation that you sought to.
- ✓ There is a significant relationship between type of family and Opinion of the respondents about friendliness with the locality people, Respondents depressions away from their family, Opinion of the respondents satisfy their work, Taking decisions on respondents satisfied with the food provided here, and Opinion of the respondents the mode of recreation that you sought to.
- ✓ All the factors are positively correlated which shows that while taking decision on Opinion towards the job interesting all the demographic profiles used for the study can be taken for the decision making process of the study.
- ✓ The factors are opinion of the respondents on each day work appears as though it will never end, respondents towards the working condition, opinion of the respondents the job really demanding, opinion of the respondents work involves deadlines that has to completed, respondents frequent chances to go to your hometown, taking decisions on respondents satisfied with the food provided here are taken for decision making process of the study.

Suggestions:

- ✓ The respondents said that there is no ending process in their work and the management has to reconsider it for the convenient of employees so that the quality of work will be increased in future period of time.
- ✓ The employees feel that language is one of the barrier in work place and for this the management can coordinate the employees based on their language so that a friendly atmosphere will be created in working place which leads to increase in productivity of the firm.
- ✓ Based on the analysis the factors opinion of the respondents on each day work appears as though it will never end, respondents towards the working condition, opinion of the respondents the job really demanding, opinion of the respondents work involves deadlines that has to completed, respondents frequent chances to go to your hometown, taking decisions on respondents satisfied with the food provided here are taken for decision making process of the study.

Conclusion:

The conclusion is that they can carry out a workplace audit to assess stress levels and they can develop policies and procedures that support employee well being and the employees also feel that language is one of the barrier in work place and for this the management can coordinate the employees based on their language so that a friendly atmosphere will be created in working place which leads to increase in productivity of the firms with IT industry.

References:

1. Andrewsp. Ochtinsky, "The role of stress in psychological disorder" Rochester institute of technology Vol: 5, No: 4/October 1988.
2. Peter R. Vagg, Charles D. Spielberger and carol F. Wasala, "Effects on organization level and gender on Stress in working place" ,International journal of stress management , Vol 9, October 2002
3. G. Gnanaselvi & Dr. S. Shanmugapriya, "Job Stress among Women Employees", International Journal of Current Research and Modern Education, Volume 3, Issue 1, Page Number 170-174, 2018.
4. A-S. Antoniou, F. Polychroni, A. N. Vlachakis, "Gender and age differences in occupational stress and professional burnout between primary and high-school teachers in Greece" Journal of managerial psychology, Vol 21 Iss: 7, 2006, pp.682.

5. K. Veerakumar (2016) article titled “A Study on Impact of Customer Satisfaction on Brand Loyalty” International Journal of Scientific Research and Modern Education, Vol-I, Issue-I, June – 2016. P.No.661-663.
6. Patrica Loft, Mark G. Thomas, Keith J. Petriea, Roger J. Booth,Jeremy Miles and Kavita “Examination stress result in altered cardiovascular responses to acute challenge and lower Cortisols”, Psycho neuroendocrinology, Volume 32,Issue 4,May 2007,Page 367
7. Routledge, “Work and Stress”, Journal of European Academy of Occupational Health Psychology, Volume 24, 2009.